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Legal Regime for Environmental, Social and Governance Considerations Under Bilateral Investment Treaties in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the evolving integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations within Nigeria's Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs), highlighting their significance for sustainable development and responsible foreign investment. Using a doctrinal research methodology, the paper analyzes Nigeria's BITs with countries such as China, France, Italy, the UK, and Morocco, focusing on ESG incorporation and regulatory implications. Findings reveal that while earlier treaties lacked ESG provisions, recent agreements like the Nigeria–Morocco BIT impose binding obligations on investors, mandating environmental and social impact assessments, adherence to labor and human rights standards, and corporate accountability. However, enforcement challenges, regulatory gaps, and potential investor resistance to stricter compliance remain critical obstacles. The study concludes that effective ESG integration can align foreign investment with Nigeria's sustainable development goals, improve investor accountability, and protect sovereign regulatory space. It recommends constitutional recognition of ESG rights, enforceable ESG clauses in BITs, enhanced institutional capacity, stakeholder engagement, and the establishment of ESG-specific tribunals and grievance mechanisms. These measures are essential to foster transparency, legal clarity, and long-term resilience in Nigeria's investment regime, making the country a more attractive and ethically aligned destination for global investors.

Keywords: Environmental, Treaties, Sustainable Development, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Over the course of the past few decades, Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) considerations have dominated global discourse as obligations businesses and investments should pursue towards promoting sustainable development. Beginning from 1992 during the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, global discussions have emphasised the need to integrate environmental sustainability practices into development activities and exploitation of nature's endowments across States.¹ ESG has been in use for more than a decade as a label for a range of factors that are relevant in assessing whether an economic activity is sustainable for the purposes of investment decision making.² These factors have been used especially by large investors and asset managers to decide on allocation of capital with a view to ensuring sustainability and financial performance over the long term.³

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¹ C G Borges and Others, 'CSG and Investment Treaties in Africa: A New Substantive Standard?' (26 March 2024) <<https://www.iflr.com/article/2d0uopymt62ksjkl4e39c/sponsored/esg-and-investment-treaties-in-africa-a-new-substantive-standard>> accessed 10 October 2024.

² O Shasore and O Uka, 'The Importance of ESG and Its Effect on International Arbitration', The Alpine Review, 2 <<https://www.alp.company/sites/default/files/ALP%20Review%20%20The%20Importance%20of%20ESG%20and%20its%20effect%20on%20International%20Arbitration.pdf>> accessed 19 October 2024.

³ *Ibid.*

International Investment Agreements (IIAs) including Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) are incorporating ESG matters including specific provisions on the protection of the environment, climate action and Sustainable Development.⁴ The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) notes that many recent BITs capture ESG concerns such as environmental protection, labour laws, and transparency requirements as part of the overall sustainable development agenda.⁵ OECD members have clearly embraced ESG in their BITs. Canada and the United States (US) are leading examples of OECD countries that have incorporated ESG in their BITs. For Canada, the Canadian Model Agreement for the Promotion and Protection of Investments recognises the role of investments in promoting sustainable development as part of responsible business conduct.⁶

Similarly, the US Model Bilateral International Investment Treaty (BIT) recognises the nexus between BITs and ESG matters such as the environment and human rights including labour rights.⁷ The US Model BIT stipulates that investments shall be conducted in a manner that respects environmental laws and policies of the host State, and multilateral environmental agreements.⁸ ESG guidelines and standards have also been deployed in the aspect of environmental protection. For instance, the US Model BIT prescribes that it is inappropriate to encourage investment by weakening or reducing the protections afforded in domestic environmental laws.⁹ In addition, the US Model BIT stipulates that investments shall be conducted in a manner that complies with domestic labour standards as well as the international labour standards articulated under the International Labour Organization (ILO) Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and its Follow-Up.¹⁰

Many regional political and economic organisations are capturing ESG concerns in their investment agreements such as protection of human rights and the environment, compliance with domestic law, measures against corruption and the promotion of sustainable development. The African Union has adopted the Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)¹¹ which seeks to achieve, among other things, the promotion and attainment of sustainable development in States Parties through responsible and transparent investments. Another regional body that has embraced the integration of ESG considerations in investment contracts is the Southern African Development Community (SADC). The SADC Model BIT Template encapsulates ESG concerns including human rights, environment and labour issues. The SADC Model BIT Template requires that investors and their investments have a duty to respect human rights in the workplace and in the community and State in which they are located.¹²

The SADC Model Bilateral Investment Treaty Template also stipulates that investors and their investments shall act in accordance with core labour standards as required by the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights of Work and that further investors and their investments shall not establish, manage or operate investments in a manner inconsistent with international environmental,

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ OECD, *ESG Investing: Practices, Progress and Challenges* (Paris: OECD Publishing 2020) 1 <<https://doi.org/10.1787/5504598c-en>> accessed 20 October 2024; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 'Novel Features in Recent OECD Bilateral Investment Treaties.' *International Investments Perspectives*, 2006.

⁶ Government of Canada, 'Model Agreement for the Promotion and Protection of Investments, 2021' <https://www.international.gc.ca/trade-commerce/trade-agreements-accordscommerciaux/agr-acc/fipa-apie/2021_model_fipa-2021_modele_apie.aspx?lang=eng> accessed 22 October 2024

⁷ United States of America, 'Model Bilateral Investment Treaty, 2012' <<https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/BIT%20text%20for%20ACIEP%20Meeting.pdf>> accessed 21 October 2024

⁸ *Ibid.*, art 12

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, art 13

¹¹ African Union, 'Agreement Establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area' <https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36437-treaty-consolidated_text_on_cfta_-_en.pdf> accessed 21 October 2024

¹² International Institute for Sustainable Development, 'Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) Model Bilateral Investment Treaty Template' <<https://www.iisd.org/itn/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/sadc-model-bit-templatefinal.pdf>> accessed 22 October 2024.

labour, and human rights obligations binding on the host State or the home State, whichever obligations are higher¹³

Within the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) sub-region, the ECOWAS Common Investment Code (ECOWIC) was adopted in 2018 by the Member States to regulate investment incorporates ESG provisions into the Code. For instance, ECOWIC requires investors and the home State to commit to environmental protection and the adoption of sound environmental practices and sustainable development measures in conducting their business operations and relationships.¹⁴ Investors are to comply with all national laws of the host States and in some cases, international best practices in environmental protection and sustainability.¹⁵ ECOWIC also integrates obligations of investors to the host States in the areas of labour practices,¹⁶ development objectives and social responsibility,¹⁷ socio-political obligations,¹⁸ consumer protection,¹⁹ corporate governance and responsible business conduct,²⁰ corruption and unethical practices.²¹ The foregoing buttresses the point that ESG considerations are no longer optional requirements in the conduct of international business but have become inextricable elements of international investment law.

Nigeria has BITs with a host of countries cutting across Africa, Europe and Asia. Nigeria does not have such agreement with the US at the moment, although efforts to establish investment relations with the US began in 2000 with the signing of a Trade and Investment Framework Agreement (TIFA) by both governments.²² Fifteen of Nigeria's BITs have been ratified.²³

However, it has been observed that some foreign investors under BITs have engaged in bad governance practices thus affecting the attainment of the 'G' pillar of the ESG agenda.²⁴ Such practices include corruption, lack of diversity and failure to embrace Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).²⁵ It is thus imperative for investors to adopt good governance practices in order to enhance the role of ESG in BITs.

Examination of Some Specific Nigerian Bilateral Investment Treaties

Nigeria is taking meaningful steps to incorporate ESG considerations into its BITs, moving from a purely investor-centric model to one that balances investor protection with sustainable development. Some of the BITs of Nigeria will be discussed below.

Nigeria-China Bilateral Investment Treaties

Nigeria and China, two prominent players in their respective fields, have established strong bilateral ties over time. This relationship is based on shared economic interests and diplomatic collaboration, with both nations benefiting from trade deals and cultural exchanges. Nigeria frequently turns to China for infrastructure development projects, while China sees Nigeria as an important partner in growing its influence in Africa. China's involvement in African problems dates back to the 1950s. During that period, African republics began to liberate themselves from colonialism. As a result, China's connection with Africa in modern times has been marked by the former's backing for liberation movements that were at the time in critical phases, culminating in the liberation of the bulk of African states from

¹³ *Ibid*, art 15

¹⁴ ECOWIC, arts 21-29

¹⁵ *Ibid*

¹⁶ *Ibid*, art 30

¹⁷ *Ibid*, art 31

¹⁸ *Ibid*, art 32

¹⁹ *Ibid*, art 33

²⁰ *Ibid*, art 34

²¹ ECOWIC art 35-37

²² US Departments of State, '2024 Investment Climate Statements: Nigeria'

<<https://www.state.gov/reports/2024-investment-climate-statements/nigeria/>> accessed 20 October 2024.

²³ These include BITs with China, France, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Republic of Korea, the Netherlands, Romania, Serbia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, and the UK.

²⁴ I Filatotchev and G K Stahl, 'Towards Transnational CSR. Corporate Social Responsibility Approaches and Governance Solutions for Multinational Corporations' *Organizational Dynamics*, (2015) (44)(2) 121-129.

²⁵ *Ibid*.

colonial domination in the 1960s. The initial motivations for China's backing were ideological, but this would shift over the next few decades.²⁶

Nigeria and China since the late 1950s, recognized and actual bilateral relations between the two countries did not begin until 1971.²⁷ Since then, their commercial links have increased rapidly. According to Ibrahim and Sari,²⁸ Nigeria and China's commercial relationship, which has grown from early collaboration in science and technology to other areas, is one of the best in Africa since Nigeria serves as a viable market for China.

The Nigeria–China BIT, signed in 2001, is one of Nigeria's older investment treaties and reflects the traditional approach to investment protection. As with many BITs of its era, this treaty focuses heavily on investor rights with minimal attention to host state regulatory flexibility or ESG issues. The treaty provides robust protections for Chinese investors in Nigeria and vice versa. Article 2 of the Treaty provided that investments of the investors of either Contracting Party shall enjoy the continuous protection in the territory of the other Contracting Party.²⁹ Subject to its laws and regulations, neither Contracting Party shall take any unreasonable or discriminatory measures against the management, maintenance, use, enjoyment and disposal of the investments by the investors of the other Contracting Party.³⁰ This provision makes no reference to ESG factors.

Article 4 provides compensation guarantees for direct or indirect expropriation. Thus, neither Contracting Party shall expropriate, nationalize or take similar measures against the investments of investors of the other Contracting Party in its territory, unless the following conditions are met: (a) for the public interests; (b) under domestic legal procedure; (c) without discrimination; (d) against fair compensation.³¹ However, it does not allow for regulatory carve-outs in cases of environmental or public health regulation.

Article 8 allows foreign investors to bring disputes to ICSID or UNCITRAL arbitration without requiring prior exhaustion of local remedies or compliance with ESG standards. Where the Contracting Parties cannot reach an agreement within twelve months, the dispute shall, upon request of either Contracting Party, be submitted to an arbitral tribunal of three members. Each Contracting Party shall appoint one arbitrator, and those two arbitrators shall nominate a third arbitrator who shall be a national of a third State with diplomatic relations with the Contracting Parties. The third arbitrator shall be appointed by the two Contracting Parties as the Chairman of the arbitral tribunal.³²

The Nigeria–China BIT 2001 does not contain any explicit references to environmental protection, social standards, or governance principles. It does not require Environmental or Social Impact Assessments (ESIAs) or mention Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) or contain language on anti-corruption, labor rights, or human rights. The absence of such provisions in the Nigeria–China BIT raises the risk where Nigeria may hesitate to enforce ESG laws for fear of violating treaty obligations and incurring liability in ISDS.

Nigeria-France Bilateral Investment Treaties

Nigeria and France have maintained bilateral investment relations for decades, culminating in the signing of a BIT in 1990. The Nigeria–France BIT reflects the traditional investment treaty model, focused primarily on investment protection and promotion, with little to no emphasis on ESG standards. Article 2 deals with the promotion and protection of investments. Hence,

²⁶ A Abiodun, *Nigeria and the BRICs: Diplomatic, Trade, Cultural and Military Relations* (Johannesburg: South African Institute of International Affairs, 2011).

²⁷ M Oke et al, 'Nigeria-China trade relations: Projections for National Growth and Development' *International Journal of Business and Management*, (2019) (14)(11); Z Gimba and S G Ibrahim, 'China-Nigeria Economic Relations: The Need for Greater Resource Management for Development' *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, (2018) (2)(3), 176-188; P Utomi, *China and Nigeria* (Washington, DC: Centre for Strategic and International Studies, 2008).

²⁸ K H Ibrahim and D W Sari, 'Nigeria-China: An Examination of Recent Bilateral Trade Relations' *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, (2019) (1)(5), 172-184.

²⁹ Nigeria–China BIT, 2001 art 2(2)

³⁰ *Ibid*, art. 2(3)

³¹ *Ibid*, art. 4(1)

³² Nigeria–China BIT, 2001 art. 8(2)

both parties agree to encourage and protect investments made in their territories,³³ ensuring “fair and equitable treatment” without discrimination.³⁴

According to article 5, the Contracting Parties shall not take any measure of expropriation or nationalization or any other measure the effect of which is to dispossess.³⁵ Also, Contracting Parties shall not take expropriation or nationalization measures or any other measures the effect of which is to dispossess, directly or indirectly, investors of the other Party of investments belonging to them in their territory and in their maritime zone, except in the public interest and provided that such measures are not discriminatory or contrary to any particular undertaking.³⁶

Furthermore, any investment-related dispute between one of the Contracting Parties and an investor from the other Party should, as much as possible, be resolved amicably between the parties involved. If the dispute is not resolved within six months from the date it was first raised by either party, it may be referred at the request of either party to arbitration before the ICSID.³⁷ The 1990 Nigeria–France BIT does not include any express ESG-related provisions, which is typical of treaties concluded before the 2000s.

Nigeria-Italy Bilateral Investment Treaties

The Nigeria–Italy Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT), signed in 2000 and entered into force in 2005, is a key legal framework governing investment relation between the two countries. Article 2 provided for the promotion and protection of investments. Thus, each Contracting Party shall encourage investors of the other Contracting Party to invest in its territory and shall admit such investments in accordance with its legislation.³⁸ Also, each Contracting Party, within the bounds of its own territory, shall offer investments effected by, and the income accruing to, investors of the other Contracting Party no less favourable treatment than that accorded to investments effected by, and income accruing to, its own investors or investors of any Third State.³⁹

Additionally, investments of investors of one Contracting Party shall not be directly or indirectly nationalized, expropriated, requisitioned or subjected to any measures having similar effects in the territory of the other Contracting Party, except for public purposes, or national interest, against immediate full and effective compensation and, where such measures are taken, they should be on a non-discriminatory basis and in conformity with the legal provisions and procedures.⁴⁰ Under these provisions, it is clear that an act of expropriation could either be direct or indirect. While direct expropriation is the outright and explicit taking of property of a foreign investor,⁴¹ indirect/regulatory expropriation includes any regulatory measure taken by the government that restricts the right of a foreign investor over its investment.⁴² However, the effect of globalization and the increasing existence of an extensive body of law on FDI make direct expropriation increasingly rare.⁴³

Investors are allowed to bring disputes before the ICSID or through ad hoc arbitration under UNCITRAL rules if disputes are not resolved amicably within six months. In the event that the dispute between the Contracting Parties cannot be settled within six months from the date on which one of the Contracting Parties notifies, in writing, the other Contracting Party, the dispute shall, at the request of one of them, be laid before an ad hoc Arbitration Tribunal as provided in this Article.⁴⁴

Nigeria-United States Bilateral Investment Treaties

The Nigeria–United States BIT was signed February 16, 2000. It is one of Nigeria’s most significant BITs, given the strategic political and economic relationship between the two countries. The treaty

³³ Nigeria–France BIT, 1990 art. 2

³⁴ *Ibid*, art. 3

³⁵ *Ibid*, art. 5(2)(i)

³⁶ *Ibid*, art. 5(2)(ii)

³⁷ Nigeria–France BIT, 1990 art. 8

³⁸ Nigeria–Italy BIT art. 2(1)

³⁹ Nigeria–Italy BIT art. 3(1)

⁴⁰ *Ibid*, art. 5(2)

⁴¹ D Collins, *An Introduction to International Investment Law* (Cambridge: University Printing Press, 2017) at 35.

⁴² *Ibid*, 162.

⁴³ S Subedi, *International Investment Law: Reconciling Policy and Principles* (2nd edn, Portland: Hart Publishing, 2012) 88.

⁴⁴ Nigeria–Italy BIT arts. 8 and 9

reflects the U.S. Model BIT (1987 and 1994 versions), which prioritizes strong investor protections and ISDS mechanisms, while offering limited ESG safeguards. However, according to the treaty, for the purposes of further developing bilateral trade and investment and providing for a steady increase in the exchange of goods and services, the Parties will consider whether further agreements relating to trade, taxation, intellectual property, labor, transfer of technology, technical cooperation, and investment issues would be desirable.⁴⁵

While the treaty was progressive for its time, it lacks binding ESG obligations. However, there are two notable soft law-style provisions. Either Party may seek the views of civil society, such as business, labor, consumer, environmental, and academic groups, on matters related to the work of the Council whenever the Party considers it appropriate.⁴⁶ Furthermore, any dispute between the Parties relating to the implementation and interpretation of this Agreement will be resolved through consultations and negotiations.⁴⁷

Nigeria-United Kingdom Bilateral Investment Treaties

The Nigeria–United Kingdom BIT was signed on December 11, 1990, and entered into force on January 1, 1991. It reflects the UK’s standard investment treaty model from the late 20th century, which prioritizes strong protections for foreign investors, particularly in sectors such as oil and gas, telecommunications, and infrastructure. According to the Treaty, each party shall, within the scope of its available resources, promote and provide favorable conditions for nationals or companies of the other Party to invest capital within its territory. While retaining the right to exercise powers granted under its domestic laws, it shall allow the entry of such capital. This Agreement shall apply only to investments whether made before or after its entry into force that have received written approval from the relevant Contracting Party, where such approval is legally required. The investment must comply with the laws in effect within the territory of the approving Party and with any conditions attached to that approval.⁴⁸

Investors are to be treated at least as well as domestic or third-country investors.⁴⁹ Expropriation is only permitted if done for a public purpose, in a non-discriminatory manner, under due process of law, and with prompt, adequate, and effective compensation.⁵⁰ Investors can refer disputes to ICSID or other agreed arbitral tribunals after six months of unsuccessful negotiations.⁵¹

The existing BIT is from 1990. It covers only investment protection, without introducing modern provisions on the environment, health and labour standards, and it does not limit the action of Investor–State Dispute Settlement (ISDS) through the right of governments to regulate. Moreover, it does not include provisions on investment facilitation and promotion, something that Nigeria is including in its most recent BITs.⁵² UK investment is particularly limited to large greenfield investments in the oil and gas sector and small investments made by the British Nigerian community. Portfolio investment is limited because of the reduced number of listed securities. There are limited facilities for small investors from both Nigeria and the UK, such as franchises.⁵³

Nigeria-South Africa Bilateral Investment Treaties

Nigeria and South Africa, two of Africa’s largest economies, signed a BIT on April 29, 2000, which entered into force on July 27, 2005.⁵⁴ The treaty was intended to promote and protect investments between the two countries, enhancing economic cooperation and integration within the African continent. However, like many early 2000s BITs, this agreement lacks explicit ESG provisions. This

⁴⁵ Nigeria–United States BIT art. 6

⁴⁶ *Ibid*, art. 5

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, art. 9

⁴⁸ Nigeria–United Kingdom BIT art. 2(1)

⁴⁹ *Ibid*, art. 3

⁵⁰ *Ibid*, art. 5

⁵¹ *Ibid*, art. 9

⁵² M Mendez-Parra et al, ‘Nigeria and UK Bilateral Trade and Investment: Diagnostic, Identification of Constraints and Recommendations’ <<https://www.pdfnigeria.org/rc/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/190805ODI-UK-Nigeria-Report-058-EDF-MM-vs-0.0.pdf>> accessed 22 May 2025.

⁵³ *Ibid*.

⁵⁴ Nigeria-South Africa BIT

omission has become increasingly significant as both countries have evolved in their domestic and international commitments to sustainable development and corporate responsibility.

In accordance with the Treaty, each state commits to encourage and create favorable conditions for investment by nationals and companies of the other Party. Admittance of investments is subject to the host country's laws and approval procedures.⁵⁵ Also, investments shall be accorded fair and equitable treatment (FET) and full protection and security. Neither Party shall impair investments through arbitrary or discriminatory measures.⁵⁶ Hence, investors are entitled to treatment no less favorable than that given to nationals or to investors from third countries.⁵⁷

Expropriation is allowed only for public interest, under due process, and must be non-discriminatory with prompt, adequate, and effective compensation.⁵⁸ Additionally, any legal dispute arising between an investor of one Party and the other Party relating to an investment of the former which has not been amicably settled shall, after a period of six months from written notification of a claim, be submitted to international arbitration if the investor concerned so wishes.⁵⁹ The practice of some arbitral tribunals to neglect the impact of public purpose in their examination of an expropriation clause is partly attributed to the fact that most traditional BITs, including Nigeria's BITs, do not provide for environmental protection⁶⁰ and human rights. Therefore, in the context of public purpose, which includes environmental and human rights protection, the clause regarding expropriation in Nigeria's BITs potentially inhibits the government's ability to protect the environment and human rights.⁶¹

Extent of Incorporation of Environmental, Social and Governance Considerations in Nigerian Bilateral Investment Treaties

The incorporation of ESG considerations into Nigeria's BITs has evolved significantly, reflecting a shift towards sustainable and responsible investment practices. It has been pointed out that ESG has the ability of shaping the behavior of Multinational Corporations under BITs by fostering socially responsible, sustainable and ethical investments. ESG is thus an essential part of the international investment law regime which can foster Sustainable Development through the investment sphere by promoting responsible business conduct.

Environmental Considerations

As the operation of foreign investment began to have both environmental and human rights impacts, states started introducing provisions relating to environmental and human rights protection in their BITs to ensure responsible investments in their territory. Hence, the second generation of BITs such as the Nigeria – Austria BIT refers to environmental protection in its preamble.⁶² Nigeria – Austria BIT focuses on the commitment of state parties to achieve the BIT objectives “in a manner consistent with the protection of health, safety, and the environment, and the promotion of internationally recognised labour standards.”⁶³ Article 4 of the Nigeria–Austria BIT acknowledges the importance of environmental protection by stating that it is inappropriate to encourage investment by relaxing domestic environmental laws.⁶⁴ This provision underscores both countries' commitment to maintaining robust environmental standards and discourages the dilution of such laws to attract foreign investment. Similarly, the Nigeria-Canada BIT provides that states “recognize that it is inappropriate to encourage investment by relaxing... safety or environmental measures” and that these measures should not be

⁵⁵ Nigeria-South Africa BIT art. 3

⁵⁶ *Ibid*, art. 4

⁵⁷ *Ibid*, art. 4(3)

⁵⁸ *Ibid*, arts. 5 and 6

⁵⁹ *Ibid*, art. 8(1)

⁶⁰ Q Ren, *Public Interests in International Investment Law: Balancing Protection for Investor and Environment* (Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2018) 124.

⁶¹ The Centre for Research on Multinational Corporations Report, “Shell put Nigeria under Pressure with ISDS Process to obtain Oil Field OPL 245” <isds.bilaterals.org/?shell-put-nigeria-under-pressure> accessed 23 May 2025.

⁶² Austria- Nigeria Agreement for the Promotion and Protection of Investment between the Republic of Austria and the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 8 April, 2013.

⁶³ Nigeria–Austria BIT

⁶⁴ *Ibid*, art. 4

waived in order to encourage the operation of foreign investment.⁶⁵ The FIPA encourages investors to voluntarily adhere to internationally recognized standards of corporate social responsibility. This includes considerations related to labour, the environment, human rights, community relations, transparency, and anti-corruption.⁶⁶

The recent Nigeria-Morocco BIT represents a third-generation BIT.⁶⁷ The treaty also aims to prevent investors from circumventing international environmental, labour, and human rights obligations.⁶⁸ According to the agreement, the Parties recognize that their respective environmental laws policies and multilateral environmental agreements to which they are both party, play an important role in protecting the environment.⁶⁹ Article 14 mandates that investors conduct environmental and social impact assessments prior to establishing investments, adhering to the laws of the host or home state.⁷⁰ Article 18 requires investors to maintain environmental management systems, with companies in resource-intensive sectors expected to obtain ISO 14001 certification or its equivalent.

While less prescriptive than the Nigeria–Morocco BIT, the Nigeria–Singapore BIT acknowledges that it is inappropriate to encourage investment by relaxing domestic health, safety, or environmental measures.⁷¹ Accordingly, the Parties agree not to waive or derogate from such measures to attract investment. If a Party believes the other has offered such encouragement, it may request consultations to address the issue.

Social Considerations

Article 5 of the Nigeria-Austria BIT addresses labour considerations, emphasizing that attracting investment should not come at the expense of weakening domestic labour laws. It outlines internationally recognized labour rights, including the right of association and collective bargaining, prohibition of forced or compulsory labour, protection against child labour, non-discrimination in employment and occupation, and the acceptable conditions of work regarding wages, hours, and occupational safety and health.⁷² These provisions align with core International Labour Organization (ILO) standards, reinforcing the treaty's commitment to upholding fundamental labour rights.

Under the Nigeria-Morocco BIT, investors must uphold human rights and comply with core labour standards as outlined in the International Labour Organization's 1998 Declaration.⁷³ The Parties acknowledge that it is unsuitable to attract investment by weakening domestic labour standards, public health, or safety measures. They agree not to waive or reduce such standards nor to offer such waivers as an incentive for the establishment, acquisition, expansion, or retention of investments within their territories. Each Party commits to ensuring that its laws and regulations provide robust protections for labour and human rights, appropriate to its unique economic and social context, and to strive for continuous improvement in these standards.⁷⁴

Article 24 encourages investors to contribute to the sustainable development of the host state and local communities through high levels of socially responsible practices, aligning with the ILO Tripartite Declaration on Multinational Enterprises and Social Policy.

Singapore emphasizes the significance of promoting businesses within its jurisdiction to voluntarily integrate internationally recognized corporate social responsibility (CSR) standards, guidelines, and principles into their internal policies, particularly those endorsed or supported by Singapore. Nigeria is expected to promote the voluntary adoption of internationally recognized CSR standards by enterprises

⁶⁵ Agreement between Canada and the Federal Republic of Nigeria for the Promotion and Protection of Investments, 6 May 2014, art. 15

⁶⁶ *Ibid*, art. 16

⁶⁷ Reciprocal Investment Promotion and Protection Agreement Between The Government of the Kingdom of Morocco and The Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 3 December 2016

⁶⁸ C G Borges et al, ESG and investment treaties in Africa: a new substantive standard? <<https://www.iflr.com/article/2d0uopvmt62ksjkl4e39c/sponsored/esg-and-investment-treaties-in-africa-a-new-substantive-standard>> accessed 24 May 2025.

⁶⁹ Nigeri-Morocco BIT art. 13(1)

⁷⁰ *Ibid*, art. 14

⁷¹ Nigeria-Singapore BIT art. 10

⁷² Nigeria-Austria BIT art. 5

⁷³ Nigeria-Morocco BIT art. 15(1)

⁷⁴ Nigeria-Morocco BIT art. 15(3-4)

operating within its jurisdiction. These standards should be reflected in their internal policies and practices, including endorsed principles covering areas such as labor, environmental protection, public health, human rights, community engagement, and anti-corruption.⁷⁵

Governance Considerations

The Nigeria-Canada BIT mandates transparency obligations for the states, requiring them to publish laws and regulations pertinent to the treaty. However, it does not impose similar transparency requirements on investors.⁷⁶ Additionally, while the treaty includes provisions related to anti-corruption, these are directed at the states and do not establish direct obligations for investors.

Article 19 of the Nigeria-Morocco BIT obliges investors to meet or exceed nationally and internationally accepted standards of corporate governance. Investments shall establish and maintain, where appropriate, local community liaison processes, in accordance with internationally accepted standards when available.⁷⁷ Notably, the Moroccan model BIT, not only enshrines these ESG obligations but also introduces a requirement for foreign investors who wish to resolve their investment disputes through arbitration: the treaty bars investors from bringing investment claims if it is found that the investment was made through some form of corruption.⁷⁸

Interestingly, the Nigeria – Morocco BIT provides for the civil liability of investors in their home states where their acts “lead to significant damage, personal injury or loss of life”⁷⁹ moving beyond the traditional reliance on counterclaims in investor-state dispute settlements. The mandatory language such as shall that is used in the Nigeria – Morocco BIT demonstrates that the provisions are framed as obligations that must be complied with by investors. Article 13 acknowledges each state's right to adopt, maintain, or enforce measures to ensure that investments are conducted in an environmentally and socially responsible manner, consistent with sustainable development goals.⁸⁰ The treaty's emphasis on ESG considerations aligns with broader international efforts to integrate sustainable development into investment practices.

The Nigeria–Morocco BIT sets a precedent in international investment law by embedding binding ESG obligations on investors, introducing robust enforcement mechanisms, and preserving the regulatory autonomy of host states. This treaty serves as a model for future agreements aiming to balance investor protections with sustainable development objectives.

The Nigeria-Singapore BIT provides a framework for resolving disputes between a Party and an investor of the other Party. Article 12 outlines the scope of disputes covered, focusing on alleged breaches of obligations under the agreement that cause loss or damage to the investor or its investment.⁸¹ While the Nigeria–Singapore BIT includes ESG-related clauses, these provisions are primarily state-oriented and largely voluntary, lacking enforceable obligations on investors. This approach aligns with a broader trend in African BITs to incorporate ESG considerations, though the extent and enforceability of such provisions vary across treaties.

Nigeria's BITs have progressively integrated ESG considerations, with the Nigeria–Morocco BIT serving as a model for embedding enforceable ESG obligations. Ongoing reforms and the development of a new model BIT further demonstrate Nigeria's commitment to aligning investment treaties with sustainable development goals.

Effects of Incorporation of Environmental, Social and Governance Considerations in Nigerian Bilateral Investment Treaties

Below is an analysis of the positive and negative effects of this incorporation.

Promotion of Sustainable Development

Integrating ESG clauses in BITs aligns foreign investments with Nigeria's sustainable development goals. The Morocco-Nigeria BIT, for instance, mandates investors to conduct environmental and social impact assessments and adhere to international labor and human rights standards. Such provisions

⁷⁵ Nigeria-Singapore BIT, 2016 art. 11

⁷⁶ Nigeria-Canada BIT art. 12

⁷⁷ Nigeria-Morocco BIT art. 19

⁷⁸ Borges et al (n 68)

⁷⁹ Nigeria-Morocco BIT art. 20

⁸⁰ Nigeria-Morocco BIT art 13(2)

⁸¹ Nigeria-Singapore BIT art. 12

ensure that investments contribute positively to the host country's development. Also, environmental disclosure allows stakeholders to access information on how the firm manages its environmental activities, like water, waste, energy, pollution, etc. This information is important to stakeholders in making quality decisions regarding their relationship with any corporate entity.⁸²

Enhanced Corporate Accountability

The inclusion of ESG obligations holds investors accountable for their environmental and social impacts. The Morocco-Nigeria BIT allows host states to initiate legal actions against investors who violate ESG commitments, even permitting civil actions in the investor's home country. This mechanism strengthens the enforcement of ESG standards. It is expected that any company that takes its stakeholders seriously by giving them access to important information will experience success managing the relationship of the stakeholders, who are also germane and important to the organization's success. This implies that corporate governance disclosure reduces information asymmetry among stakeholders and attracts more stakeholders to the firm, which also ensures the firm's operational efficiency.⁸³

Alignment with International Standards and Promotion of Labor Rights

Various international standards, adopted as best practice, require the incorporation of standards on ESG such as the UN Global Compact Principles, UN Principles on Responsible Investing, International Labour Organisation Conventions and International Financial Corporation Performance Standards.⁸⁴

By incorporating ESG considerations, Nigeria's BITs align with global norms and practices. This alignment enhances Nigeria's reputation as a responsible investment destination and may attract investors committed to sustainable practices.

The concept of sustainability reporting is said to be related to other concepts like corporate social responsibility reporting and triple bottom reporting. It is a voluntary reporting firms make to offer stakeholders additional benefits and disclosure to better understand the true value a corporation represents. By doing this, the company also gains a lot of benefits, these include good reputation, access to more capital, good governance, attracts quality workforce etc.⁸⁵

Protection of Sovereign Regulatory Space

ESG clauses safeguard Nigeria's right to regulate in the public interest. They provide exceptions that allow the state to implement necessary environmental and social regulations without breaching treaty obligations. As global interest in sustainable and ethical investment grows, Nigerian businesses have a unique opportunity to attract investors by adopting good ESG practices. The presence of regulatory frameworks, including the SEC Guidelines on Sustainable Financial Principles for the Capital Market, SEC Social Bond Rules, SEC Green Bond Rules, and CBN's Nigerian Sustainable Banking Principles (NSPB), underscores the country's commitment to encouraging ESG investing and aiding responsible business practices.⁸⁶ Nigerian businesses embark on their ESG journey, it is essential to recognize that the adoption of ESG principles is not just a trend but a strategic imperative for long-term success and resilience in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.⁸⁷

The investor-state dispute settlement mechanism in Nigeria's BITs can also have an impact on human rights protection. For instance, the case of *Korea National Oil Corporation v. Nigeria*.⁸⁸ This is an ongoing dispute arising from the Nigerian government's revocation of an oil prospecting license, which

⁸² A Ubandawaki, 'Impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance Disclosure on Firm Performance: A Case of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria (Master's Thesis, the American University in Cairo, 2024) AUC Knowledge Fountain. <<https://fount.aucegypt.edu/etds/2225>> accessed 25 May 2025.

⁸³ B A Alareeni and A Hamdan, 'ESG Impact on Performance of US S&P 500- Listed 55 Firms' *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society* (2020) 7.

⁸⁴ Aluko and Oyeboode, 'The ABC of ESG', <<https://www.aluko-oyebode.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/THE-ABC-OF-ESG-ALUKO-OYEBODE-GRC-JUNE-PUBLICATION.pdf>> accessed 25 May 2025.

⁸⁵ Ubandawaki (n 82)

⁸⁶ S Timi-Koleolu and Q Ogunjimi, 'ESG Investing: A Guide to Attracting Investors', <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/corporate-governance/1472310/esg-investing-a-guide-to-attracting-investors>> accessed 25 May 2025.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸⁸ ICSID Case No. ARB/23/19

was subsequently upheld by the Supreme Court on procedural grounds. The revoked licences allegedly constitute a breach of the Nigeria-Republic of Korea Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) of 1997. Although Cordes and others⁸⁹ argue that investment tribunals tend to avoid addressing the conflicting obligations that a state has under human rights and investment treaties, Kube and Petersmann argue that a host state can rely on its human rights obligation in a counterclaim to defend a denial of protection.⁹⁰ Despite the positive ESG has on BITs of Nigeria, stricter ESG obligations may deter some investors concerned about increased compliance costs and potential liabilities. The additional requirements could be perceived as barriers to investment, particularly in sectors with significant environmental impacts. While ESG provisions exist, enforcing them can be problematic. For example, the Morocco-Nigeria BIT requires disputes to be assessed by a Joint Committee and mandates the exhaustion of domestic remedies before international arbitration. These procedural steps may delay justice and complicate enforcement.

Furthermore, incorporating ESG considerations may increase the risk of disputes if investors perceive ESG-related regulations as expropriatory or discriminatory. Such disputes can be costly and may strain Nigeria's legal and financial resources. Companies may engage in superficial and false ESG reporting to create a positive image without making any significant improvement to their practices.⁹¹ There is the possibility that ESG reporting may not accurately reflect the company's true sustainability performance in the absence of reliable and verifiable assurance mechanism.

The integration of ESG considerations into Nigeria's BITs represents a progressive step towards responsible investment and sustainable development. While it offers numerous benefits, including enhanced corporate accountability and alignment with international standards, it also presents challenges related to enforcement, potential deterrence of investment, and legal ambiguities. Careful drafting, clear definitions, and robust enforcement mechanisms are essential to maximize the positive impacts while mitigating the negatives.

CONCLUSION

The integration of ESG considerations into Nigeria's BITs remains a critical yet dense endeavor that is essential for fostering sustainable and responsible foreign investment. The current legal and institutional framework presents significant challenges, including the absence of constitutional recognition of ESG rights, inadequate sector-specific legislation, and limited institutional capacity to enforce ESG standards effectively. Despite these obstacles, recent treaty provisions, such as the 2016 Morocco-Nigeria BIT, demonstrate a progressive shift toward embedding ESG obligations within international agreements. Despite these challenges, the prospects for ESG mainstreaming in Nigeria's investment landscape remain promising. Legal reforms such as constitutional recognition of ESG rights, the enactment of a comprehensive foreign investment law with ESG integration, liberalization of public interest litigation frameworks, and the domestication of regional instruments like the Pan-African Investment Code and the ECOWAS Common Investment Code can significantly strengthen ESG protections. Additionally, fostering public awareness, improving civic engagement, enhancing the operational capacity of regulatory institutions, and imposing stiffer penalties for ESG violations are critical steps towards building a robust ESG culture in Nigeria. As Nigeria continues to open its economy and seek foreign partnerships, aligning its legal and policy frameworks with regional and international ESG standards will be crucial in attracting reputable investors committed to sustainable practices. Eventually, a strategic and holistic approach, rooted in legal clarity, institutional strength, and regional cooperation, is essential for Nigeria to fully realize the potentials of ESG integration in its BITs, paving the way for a more sustainable, equitable, and resilient economic future.

⁸⁹ K Cordes et al, 'Land Deal Dilemmas: Grievances, Human Rights and Investor Protections' Columbia Center on Sustainable Investment <http://ccsi.columbia.edu/files/2016/03/CCSI_Land-deal-dilemmas.pdf> accessed 25 May 2025.

⁹⁰ K Cordes et al, 'Land Dilemmas: Grievances, Human Rights and Investor Protections', <ccsi.columbia.edu/files/2016/03/CCSI_Land-deal-dilemmas.pdf> accessed 29 May 2025; V Kube and E U Petersmann, 'Human Rights Law in International Investment Arbitration' *Asian J WTO and Intl Health L & Policy*, (2016) (11), 65-80.

⁹¹ S Kotsantonis and G Serafeim, 'Four things no one will tell you about ESG data' *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, (2019) (31)(2), 50-58.

Increasingly, ESG and sustainability are also informing investment decisions, opening new markets and sources of funding which can only be accessed through the integration of ESG strategies. It is therefore an imperative for companies and organisations to embrace ESG. It is also essential to determine the ESG approach most suitable and tailored to the company or organisation's needs, size, business/industry, and attendant risks. To ensure this, it is expedient to adopt the key elements of ESG compliance (ESG Identification and Analysis, ESG Program Design and Execution, ESG Assurance and Monitoring, ESG Capacity Building, ESG Reporting and ESG Due Diligence).

RECOMMENDATIONS

This research proceeds to make the following recommendations:

- i. The Nigerian government should enhance administrative remedies by establishing specialized ESG claims tribunals, community grievance mechanisms, and environmental ombudsman offices. Additionally, liberalize locus standi rules to enable environmental NGOs, civil society groups, and affected communities to initiate ESG-related legal actions.
- ii. The Nigerian government should however enact constitutional amendments to explicitly recognize fundamental ESG rights, including environmental protection, social welfare, and corporate accountability. This constitutional recognition will strengthen the legal enforcement of ESG obligations and provide a robust foundation for embedding these rights into domestic and international legal frameworks.
- iii. Ensure ESG clauses in BITs are enforceable, with robust legal frameworks and effective remedies. Also, promote stakeholder engagement and transparency in ESG reporting to reduce information asymmetry and build trust among investors, communities, and regulators.
- iv. To address the challenges of ESG integration in Nigeria, it is essential to strengthen the country's institutional capacity and regulatory frameworks dedicated to ESG compliance, including increasing funding, providing targeted training for enforcement agencies, and establishing clear, enforceable standards aligned with international best practices. Moreover, enhancing transparency and promoting meaningful stakeholder engagement, especially involving local communities affected by foreign investments, will ensure more inclusive decision-making and accountability.